

Designing Mathematics Lesson Plans for Primary School Students Through Experiential Education Activities

Dr. Doan Thi My Linh ✉
Thu Dau Mot University, Viet Nam

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Abstract

This article investigates the theoretical foundations of experiential education and its application in designing mathematics lesson plans for primary school students. Grounded in experiential learning theory, the study demonstrates that experiential instruction effectively promotes students' active engagement, cognitive development, and ability to apply knowledge in meaningful contexts. Using the four stages of experiential learning—concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation—the study proposes a Grade 3 mathematics lesson plan on *Measuring Lengths: Practicing Measuring Real Objects*. The lesson is organized into a sequence of experiential activities, including estimating lengths, measuring and comparing results, formulating measurement rules, and applying these rules to new situations. The design ensures visual accessibility, alignment with the cognitive characteristics of young learners, and the development of measurement competence, tool-handling skills, and problem-solving ability. Findings indicate that integrating experiential education into mathematics instruction enhances students' learning motivation, measurement accuracy, self-regulated learning, and capacity to transfer knowledge to real-world contexts. The study provides theoretical grounding and practical implications for teachers designing competency-oriented mathematics lessons.

Keywords: *Mathematics Teaching, Experiential Education Model, Primary School Students, Instructional Activity Design, Length Measurement.*

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Introduction

In the context of the current reform of general education, the shift from content-based instruction to competency-based teaching has become an essential requirement. The 2018 General Education Curriculum emphasizes that students should “experience, explore, and apply knowledge to real-life contexts through diverse learning activities” (Ministry of Education and Training, 2018). This shift requires teachers not only to master subject knowledge but also to

design experiential learning activities that create opportunities for students to actively participate and construct their own understanding.

For primary school students—who are characterized by concrete operational thinking and a natural curiosity—experiential learning plays an especially important role. Previous research has shown that children learn more effectively when they engage in hands-on activities connected to familiar, real-world situations (Kolb, 1984; Dewey, 1938). Experiential learning not only promotes deeper

conceptual understanding but also develops essential competencies such as problem-solving, communication and collaboration, critical thinking, and the ability to apply knowledge in practice (Moon, 2004; Silberman, 2015).

Mathematics in primary education is often considered an abstract subject, and many students experience difficulties in learning when knowledge is presented only through passive observation and memorization. Integrating the experiential learning model into mathematics instruction enables students to access mathematical concepts through activities such as measuring, manipulating objects, modeling, educational games, and solving real-life situations. These activities provide opportunities for students to develop mathematical concepts naturally, grounded in personal experience and specific contexts (Bruner, 1966; Clements & Sarama, 2009).

For many years, numerous researchers have examined and applied experiential learning in education with the aim of improving student learning outcomes. As early as 1925, John Dewey explored theories related to the formation of knowledge through experience (Dewey, 1925). Subsequent scholars continued to investigate this issue. Jean Piaget identified the nature and origins of human knowledge as the product of interactions between the individual and the environment (Piaget, 1972). Edgar Dale argued that learners retain more information through what they *do* as opposed to what they merely “hear,” “read,” or “observe” (Dale, 1969). In 1984, building on studies by Dewey, Lewin, Piaget, Vygotsky, and other researchers on experience and experiential-based learning, David Kolb proposed that “learning is the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience” (Kolb, 2014). Cameron Atkinson similarly emphasized that experiential learning is essentially learning by doing, in which learners actively participate in the educational process rather than remain passive recipients (Atkinson, 2017).

In Vietnam, many studies have applied experiential learning models in organizing educational activities. Pham Thanh Phuong discussed key aspects of David Kolb’s

experiential learning theory and proposed processes for designing experiential activities to teach natural numbers to Grade 2 students (Pham Thanh Phuong, 2017). Nguyen Thi Thu Ha suggested several experiential-based methods for teaching geometry-related problem solving to Grade 5 students following Lewin’s model (Nguyen Thi Thu Ha, 2018). Le Thi Cam Nhung addressed theoretical issues related to organizing experiential activities for students—including primary school learners—and presented various forms of experiential learning as well as approaches to implementing experiential activities in geometry lessons (Le Thi Cam Nhung, 2018). Tran Doan Vinh proposed the design of experiential learning activities in primary informatics education aligned with competency development (Tran Doan Vinh, 2018).

However, in practice, many primary school teachers still encounter difficulties in designing experiential-oriented lesson plans; the activities often remain fragmented, lack coherence, or fail to align with competency-development goals. Therefore, examining and developing mathematics lesson plans based on the experiential education model is essential. Such efforts not only meet the requirements of curriculum reform but also contribute to improving instructional quality and increasing students’ learning motivation.

Research Results

Mathematics Content Suitable for Experiential Learning

Table 1. Mathematics Content Applicable to Experiential Learning Approaches

Topic	Experiential Activities
Numbers and Operations (Nguyen Ang et al., 2022)	Collecting real objects to add/subtract; matching counting sticks; “mini supermarket” for calculating costs
Geometry	Creating tangram shapes; measuring real objects; building models with LEGO
Quantities and Measurement (Nguyen Ang et al., 2022)	Measuring classmates’ height; measuring distances in the schoolyard; measuring water using cups

Statistics and Probability (Nguyen Ang et al., 2022)	Collecting data on classmates with a specific characteristic; dice-rolling games
Solving Word Problems (Nguyen Ang et al., 2022)	Role-playing as customers; simulating real-life situations

Experiential Learning Model

- The diamond-shaped experiential education model proposed by Itin illustrates the distinction between students’ experiential participation—through which they derive knowledge and skills—and the teacher’s role in organizing educational activities. The model highlights four stages (concrete experience, reflection on actions and experiences, abstract conceptualization of knowledge derived from reflection, and applying newly abstracted knowledge to practice), all mediated by the learning environment and instructional materials (Itin, 1999).
- For students’ participation in experiential activities, learners first engage in

concrete experiences, then reflect on these experiences in relation to the knowledge presented in the instructional materials. Through this reflection, they abstract relevant concepts and subsequently apply the newly formed knowledge within the designed learning environment (Itin, 1999).

- For teachers’ organization of experiential education activities, teachers create concrete experiences for students and reflect on these experiences in connection with the design of the learning environment to ensure alignment with the intended educational goals. Based on this reflection, teachers structure educational activities that guide students through the processes of abstracting knowledge and applying it to real-world situations consistent with the requirements of the curriculum materials (Itin, 1999). The diamond-shaped experiential education model proposed by Itin is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Diamond-Shaped Experiential Education Model Proposed
Source: Itin, 1999

Based on Itin’s experiential education model, the roles of teachers and learners in the process of

organizing experiential learning activities can be described as follows:

Table 2. Roles of Teachers and Students in the Experiential Teaching–Learning Process

Step	Core Content	Teacher’s Role	Student’s Role
1.Experience	Real actions	Create situations, organize activities	Participate in tasks and experiences
2. Reflection	Observe – discuss – draw lessons	Elicit guiding questions	Compare, think, and share
3.Conceptualizatio	Form knowledge and rules	Standardize knowledge	Take notes, understand concepts
4. Application	Apply to new situations	Assign tasks, assess performance	Complete tasks, create solutions

Step 1: Experience

Learners directly engage in an authentic activity such as experimenting, measuring, observing, manipulating objects, participating in games, or solving situational tasks. This step provides the “input material” for learners to reflect upon and construct knowledge. Experiences may arise from individual engagement or group interaction.

Teachers must design learning experiences based on students’ prior experiences and ensure that these experiences are suitable for the school’s conditions. The experiential activities must align with the lesson objectives in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitudes; be feasible within the school context; and correspond to students’ interests and backgrounds. There are two types of learning experiences: **primary experience** and **secondary experience** (Jordan et al., 2008). These two types do not exist in a simple one-way relationship but mutually influence each other (Campbell, 1995). The teacher organizes activities that allow students to actively participate in the experiential process.

Step 2: Reflection

After the experiential activity, learners review the process and outcomes, analyze what they observed, compare the results with their expectations, and identify what is accurate, incorrect, or unusual. This step transforms experience into cognition through reflective thinking.

To facilitate this, the teacher creates conditions for students to engage in the experience, process the experience, and reflect on their own prior knowledge in comparison with what they have derived from the activity. From this reflection,

learners draw out the essential requirements for applying subject knowledge to real-life situations. The teacher organizes opportunities for students to participate, analyze their experience, and extract the intended learning outcomes.

Step 3: Generalization – Concept Formation

From the reflection process, learners derive rules, concepts, formulas, or general principles. At this stage, personal experiences become “scientificized” and transformed into systematic knowledge. The teacher’s role is to standardize this knowledge and guide students in connecting newly formed concepts with their prior knowledge.

Step 4: Application

Learners apply the newly formed knowledge to new situations, solve problems, complete exercises, or carry out a small project. This step helps verify the validity of the knowledge and generates new experiences, thereby returning to Step 1 in the learning cycle. At this stage, the teacher organizes opportunities for students to apply their knowledge in novel contexts, using appropriate methods and instructional formats to enable learners to utilize their acquired knowledge and skills in solving real-life problems.

Educational outcomes are considered indicators of learner success, reflected in what learners know, understand, and are able to do in relation to the predetermined educational objectives, in comparison with their peers, or with their own previous performance (Nguyen Thi Lan Phuong, 2010; Nguyen Loc, 2011).

Designing a Mathematics Measurement Lesson Plan Based on the Experiential Education Model

Lesson: Measuring Length – Practicing Measurement with Real Objects (Mathematics, Grade 3) (Nguyen Ang et al., 2022)

Duration: 1 period (40 minutes)

Objectives:

Knowledge: Students are able to state the steps for measuring length and perform accurate measurements. They can explain the meaning of the units cm, mm, dm, and m.

Skills: Students can estimate lengths and use a ruler to measure accurately.

Attitude: Students actively participate in learning activities and demonstrate honesty when recording measurement results.

Competencies: Measurement competence, problem-solving competence, and collaboration competence.

Preparation:

Teacher

- 20–30 cm rulers, measuring tape
- Pictures illustrating correct and incorrect measuring postures
- Group activity worksheets

Students

- Ruler, notebook, pen
- Several personal items (pencil, book, pencil case)

Teaching procedures

Table 3. Mathematics Lesson Plan on Measurement Based on the Experiential Education Model

Content	Teacher's Activities	Students' Activities
ACTIVITY 1 – CONCRETE EXPERIENCE Objective: Students estimate length. Students experience estimating real-world lengths.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign the task: “Choose an object that you think is about 20 cm long.” • Set a time limit (2 minutes). • Remind students to estimate using only their eyes. • Invite students to explain their choice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select an object about 20 cm long. • Explain their choice. • Bring the object to class.
ACTIVITY 2 – REFLECTION Objective: Actively participate; record results honestly. Students recognize differences between estimation and actual measurement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask students to measure again using a ruler. • Guide: align the zero mark correctly. • Record estimation – actual measurement – deviation. • Ask guiding questions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure the object again. • Complete the worksheet. • Discuss and present results.
ACTIVITY 3 – KNOWLEDGE GENERALIZATION Objective: State steps for measurement; understand cm, mm, dm, m. Students form accurate measurement rules.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask: “What must we do to measure accurately?” • Write the 3 standard measurement steps. • Review measurement units. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State measurement rules. • Compare with teacher's notes. • Take notes.

<p>ACTIVITY 4 – EXPERIMENTATION & APPLICATION</p> <p>Objective: Develop measurement competency; measure accurately with a ruler. Students apply rules to various objects.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign the task: measure 5 objects. • Require recording: object – estimation – actual measurement – comments. • Invite students to present. • Ask extension questions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure 5 objects. • Record results. • Present to the class. 																				
<p>ACTIVITY 5 – CONSOLIDATION & ASSESSMENT</p> <p>Objective: Develop measurement competency; measure accurately. Students reflect on key ideas.</p>	<p>The teacher provides worksheets.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="480 456 1177 833"> <thead> <tr> <th>Object</th> <th>Estimation (cm)</th> <th>Actual Measurement (cm)</th> <th>Deviation</th> <th>Comments</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Pencil</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Math textbook</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Desk</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Object	Estimation (cm)	Actual Measurement (cm)	Deviation	Comments	Pencil					Math textbook					Desk					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students are able to estimate lengths with reasonable accuracy. • <input type="checkbox"/> They can compare estimations with actual measurements and explain the causes of discrepancies. • They are able to self-evaluate the accuracy of their measurements.
Object	Estimation (cm)	Actual Measurement (cm)	Deviation	Comments																		
Pencil																						
Math textbook																						
Desk																						

Conclusion

Applying the experiential learning model to teaching Mathematics in primary education—particularly within the 2018 General Education Curriculum oriented toward competency development—offers significant pedagogical value. The use of Kolb’s experiential learning cycle in lesson planning helps structure the learning process into four clear phases: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active application. The Grade 3 Mathematics lesson plan “Measuring Length: Practicing Measurement with Real Objects,” designed according to this model, demonstrates its effectiveness in fostering learning interest, enhancing hands-on practice and manipulation, and promoting students’ active exploration. At the same time, it contributes to the development of essential competencies such as measurement skills, ruler-handling proficiency, problem-solving ability, and mathematical reasoning. Students actively utilize visual learning tools (rulers, real objects, open-ended materials) and are encouraged to explore, measure, and self-evaluate their work. Therefore, teachers should proactively design diverse learning activities connected to real-life contexts, aligned with students’ psychological characteristics and developmental levels, while

meeting curriculum requirements and accommodating actual school conditions.

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